

Kantian Zombies in the Apocalypse of Rational Ethics

A Philosophical Reading of *Pluribus*

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Abstract

This article offers a philosophical reading of the television series *Pluribus* through its complex relation to the zombie film subgenre and Kantian moral philosophy. While *Pluribus* initially adopts the familiar narrative structure of zombie cinema—genetic intervention, contagion, a post-apocalyptic world, and a small group of survivors—it radically inverts the genre’s defining assumptions. Instead of depicting zombies as irrational, violent, and morally void beings, the series presents transformed humans as hyper-rational, ethically impeccable agents whose actions are governed entirely by reason. Drawing on Kant’s account of rational agency, freedom, and morality, the article interprets these figures as embodiments of a “holy will,” a will determined exclusively by reason and free from inclination. Through the character of Carol, a resistant survivor, *Pluribus* exposes the tension between rational morality and human individuality, desire, and affect. The series thus stages a Kantian apocalypse in which the full realization of rational ethics appears paradoxically inhuman, raising critical questions about autonomy, agency, and the limits of moral rationalism.

Keywords: Kantian ethics; zombie cinema; rational agency; holy will; *Pluribus*

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Plur1bus: A New Zombie Film

The first season of the series *Plur1bus*, introduced in its promotional trailers as the final work of the creator of *Breaking Bad* (Vince Gilligan), was released by Apple Tv in November 2025. The title of the series is derived from the Latin phrase *e pluribus unum* (one out of many), which is creatively condensed in the official title (*Plur1bus*) by replacing the letter *i* with the number *1*. For Americans, this Latin phrase is particularly familiar insofar as it is one of the mottos engraved on the Great Seal of the United States, referring to the formation of a unified country from the original thirteen colonies. However, the phrase can also be found in classical Latin literature, especially in Cicero's *De Officiis*, where Cicero, in outlining his ideal society, writes that nothing produces affection and intimacy as much as compatibility of character. When someone shares ideals and tastes with others, they are able to love them as themselves, and in this way, the many are united in one¹ (Cicero, 1913 1.56).

The story of the series begins in the very first episode. Carol Sturka, a female writer of popular novels, leaves a bar with her female partner and witnesses a car veering off course and colliding with a parked vehicle. She approaches the driver and sees that he is dying while experiencing strange tremors and convulsions. She calls for help from her partner, only to see that she too collapses on the ground with similar tremors and convulsions and begins to die. Anxious and panicked, Carol returns to the bar, where she encounters a horrifying scene: everyone inside is frozen in place, all experiencing the same convulsive shaking. Confused and terrified, Carol manages to take her partner to the hospital, but the same condition prevails there as well. One by one, everyone in the hospital collapses to the ground with similar tremors and apparently dies. After some time, however, they all rise from the ground in an abnormal and terrifying manner and, with movements that are stranger and more mechanical than anything expected of human behavior, advance toward Carol. Nevertheless, their conduct remains remarkably polite, friendly, and civilized.

In the very first episode, it becomes clear that the origin of these transformations lies in four extraterrestrial signals from outer space that had been detected by a space research center. One of the scientists at the center proposes an intriguing hypothesis: the signals correspond to the four nucleic acid components of a quasi-viral genetic code. Following this conjecture, the scientists attempt to reconstruct the genetic code in mice in order to understand its nature. During an accident, however, one of the mice bites a scientist, transmitting the virus. Very quickly, all others become infected as well. Driven by the infected individuals' desire to infect others, the virus spreads across the world at a staggering speed, and all human beings—except for thirteen individuals (a number which, given the phrase *e pluribus unum*, can hardly be considered accidental)—become infected. Carol is one of these thirteen survivors, and in a post-apocalyptic world she attempts to restore things to their former state. Yet this situation proves to be far more complex and fundamentally different from the familiar world typically depicted in well-known zombie films.

Zombies in Cinema

Western cinema and literature were already familiar with figures resembling zombies, particularly through the Gothic genre and German Expressionist cinema. However, the zombie as a character—specifically as a slave deprived of free will, whose agency is controlled by another—originates more directly from the legends and ritual practices of voodoo (voodoo) in Haiti. This figure was introduced into American cinematic culture especially after the United States' occupation of Haiti (1915–1934) and subsequently became material for Hollywood films (Hoermann, 2017, p. 152). Unlike other well-known Gothic figures such as the “undead” or the “vampire,” all of which emerged from older literary traditions, zombies entered cinema directly from folklore without the mediation of an established literary canon (Dendle, 2001, pp. 2–3). Early Hollywood films that depicted zombies, such as *White Zombie* (1932) and *I Walked with a Zombie* (1943), remained heavily influenced by magical traditions associated with supernatural hypnotism, in which a human being is placed under the control of a master.

A fundamental transformation in zombie cinema occurred with the low-budget *Night of the Living Dead* (1968), the groundbreaking film by George A. Romero. Romero abandoned both the master–slave relationship and the supernatural or magical origins characteristic of earlier zombie films, presenting zombies instead as humans risen from the grave, with decaying bodies, driven solely by the urge to feed on human flesh. His zombies possessed none of the sexual allure associated with classic horror figures such as Count Dracula, nor were they monsters with non-human physiognomies, nor villainous humans whose wickedness was exaggerated through grotesque makeup. Rather, Romero's monsters were semi-decomposed corpses set in motion without self-consciousness, motivated only by a survival instinct that manifests itself in the consumption of human flesh. As James B. Twitchell observes, by combining the voodoo zombie with the figure of the vampire, Romero endowed his monsters with a hybrid power, creating his zombies through a fusion of ghoulish and plague-related figures (Twitchell, 1985, p. 267).

In Romero's films, there is no longer a limited relationship between master and slave. In this respect, his work diverges both from the model found in films rooted in voodoo traditions and from other related forms, such as films inspired by *The Cabinet of Dr. Caligari* (1920), in which a human being loses self-consciousness and free will through magic or through more modern techniques such as hypnotism. His films also depart from a familiar pattern in Western literature, where a half-mad scientist creates an uncontrollable creature such as Frankenstein's monster or the Golem. Romero's zombies instead operate according to a pattern closer to that of vampirism, in that they reproduce at a terrifying and exponential rate. The emergence of zombies thus takes the form of a contagious infection capable of affecting all human beings. This feature transforms the atmosphere of his films—and of the subsequent films influenced by his work—into a post-apocalyptic setting far more horrifying than the temporary disruption of urban order caused by a single, non-replicable monster.

Although *Night of the Living Dead* (1968) contains vague references to cosmic radiation as the origin of zombie production, later films within this horror subgenre, responding to newly emergent anxieties among the general population, increasingly specified the source of contagion in

accordance with contemporary social sensitivities. For example, in *The Return of the Living Dead* (1985), the return of the ashes of incinerated zombies to natural water sources, followed by contaminated rainfall, resonates with the widespread American fear of acid rain (Juliet Lauro, 2011, p. 234). As filmmakers came to recognize that public fears surrounding nuclear experiments, genetic interventions, or viral contamination were far deeper and more realistic than fears of magic, zombie films—and even video games released after the success of the *Resident Evil* franchise in the late 1990s—gradually moved toward providing scientific explanations for the origins of zombies (Jones, 2014, p. 16). Through this shift, zombie films depict a post-apocalyptic world overrun by savage humanoid creatures devoid of any form of self-consciousness or free will, who destroy human civilization by infecting other human beings.

The World in the Tradition of the Zombie Film

Zombie films after *Night of the Living Dead* (1968) are characteristically defined by their depiction of a post-apocalyptic space in which all governmental, social, and urban structures, as well as relations among citizens, undergo radical transformation. This post-apocalyptic setting functions in particular as a lament for the loss of civilization, as its defensive bastions are dismantled one by one with the advance of the zombies. In this respect, zombie films pessimistically return to the long-standing theme of civilization and savagery. The cynical and pessimistic outlook of the zombie film subgenre thus stands in direct opposition to genres that optimistically celebrate the triumph of civilization over savagery. For instance, whereas in classical Western films the idea of westward expansion is oriented toward taming the savage and building civilization in nature (Schatz, 1981, p. 51), zombie films construct an anti-western subgenre in which the savages, through their advance, seek to destroy civilization (Olney, 2017, p. 133). This motif is directly rooted in the fear of the destruction of human civilization and the emergence of an anti-civilization.

Many critics and theorists, influenced by anti-imperialist perspectives and leftist literature, have interpreted the cultivation of this fear as a strategy employed by the Western world to suppress its intellectual rivals. For example, the loss of order in zombie films has been understood merely as the loss of the patriarchal heritage of the Western world, with Hollywood cinema exaggerating its horrific aspects in order to preserve this heritage (Wood, 1979, p. 93). Similarly, the fear of the end of the world has often been interpreted in various ways as a fear of the end of capitalism, an interpretation that becomes particularly salient in *Dawn of the Dead* (1978). In that film, zombies—understood as communists seeking to dissolve the symbols of capitalism—attack a shopping mall in which human survivors, positioned as guardians of the capitalist system, have taken refuge (Williams, 1996, p. 149) (Skal, 2001, p. 309). These critical approaches regard zombie films as a form of new capitalist propaganda aimed at preserving the status quo, representing a later and transformed version of the same imperialistic outlook already present in pre-Romero zombie films. If, in Romero's films, savage and predatory zombies assault the capitalist world, then in the latent semantic layers of classical zombie films such as *White Zombie* (1932) and *I Walked with a Zombie* (1943)—produced in accordance with voodoo traditions—humans subjected to magical rituals in mysterious and semi-savage lands such as Haiti likewise instilled fear in the imperialistic West (Olney, 2017, p. 19).

Beyond these ideological critiques, however, the horror of zombie films can be understood as referring to a more universal and higher-order fear, one that is primarily rooted in human

conceptions of normal human life and death. Living humans live, eat, and walk, while the dead are expected to remain motionless beneath the ground in eternal rest. This is a natural assumption in our understanding of human life, one that is maintained even within accepted forms of supernaturalism, such as those found in religious traditions, where the human soul must leave the body after death so that the body can undergo a natural process of decay. The return of the dead body in the form of zombies disrupts this order. In this way, humans who ought to enjoy a blissful afterlife instead experience an afterlife of horror through zombies. Human beings conceive of themselves as created in the image of God, yet they are confronted with zombies as an inverted image of themselves (Delfino & Taylor, 2012, p. 51). This constitutes a form of fear arising from a disturbance of categories. Accordingly, the horror of zombie films involves not only fear of the corpse and the visual representation of death—or what Dillard describes as the fear of “dead kindred” (Dillard, 1987, p. 15)—but also fear of the collapse of the very conceptual framework that structures our common understanding.

The apocalyptic fear in zombie films is rooted in precisely this chaos. Zombies are neither wild animals nor non-human beings such as extraterrestrial monsters; rather, they are humans without a human form of life. That is, they confront us—through a kind of existential contradiction—with a “self” that we are incapable of enduring. The fear of semi-decomposed, mobile corpses with whom no form of dialogue or negotiation is possible, and who do nothing but tear apart and reproduce, constitutes the merely visual horror that places zombie films within the category of horror cinema. Yet the fear of an apocalypse in which we are compelled to confront beings of our own kind who have undergone an intrinsic transformation is a deeper, existential fear that lies at the core of zombie films. *Pluribus* explicitly foregrounds and thematizes precisely this fear.

Pluribus and the Inversion of the Zombie Film

The series *Pluribus* shares several generic elements with zombie films. In *Pluribus*, as in many zombie films, a genetic intervention (this time of cosmic origin) transforms human beings into something other than what is commonly understood as human. Likewise, in this series—as in many zombie narratives—this intrinsic transformation spreads in a contagious manner and rapidly infects the entire world, with the exception of a small surviving minority. Moreover, the new world in *Pluribus*, much like that of zombie films, is a post-apocalyptic world in which the survivors (two of them in *Pluribus*) attempt to restore the previous state of affairs. These survivors, similar to those in zombie films who, as Max Brooks suggests, function like a government-in-exile (Brooks, 2003, p. 155), initially attempt to protect themselves from contamination by isolating themselves from society in order to preserve their humanity, and subsequently seek a way to return the world to its former form.

Nevertheless, the post-apocalyptic world of *Pluribus* cannot simply be described as a dystopia of horror; indeed, it may even be possible to discern the representation of a form of utopia within it. This is precisely what places *Pluribus* in opposition to the zombie film tradition. The transformed humans in *Pluribus* have become ideally civilized. By connecting to a kind of collective mind, they have mastered all forms of human knowledge, adhere to moral principles in a remarkably flawless manner, lack the capacity for lying or violence, do not steal, do not kill animals or plants in order to obtain food, and even strive to provide the best possible amenities to satisfy the survivors. Unlike zombies, they are never intent on killing the survivors, nor—unlike the

transformed humans in films such as *Invasion of the Body Snatchers* (1958)—do they attempt to conceal their transformed identity through deception or role-playing. They regard themselves as new humans who, following the greatest revolution in the history of human civilization, seek to establish a peaceful and civilized form of life on Earth. To such an extent, in fact, that with the exception of two individuals, nearly all of the survivors are satisfied with the new condition, in which—through the kindness and self-sacrifice of the transformed humans—they are able to fulfill their financial and sexual fantasies in a safe manner.

Yet two of the survivors, much like the survivors in zombie films, regard the new world as a dystopian post-apocalyptic reality and are willing to do anything to restore the previous order. Their reason for opposing the new apocalyptic world brings us to the most fundamental point of convergence between *Pluribus* and zombie films: the survivors perceive the humans of the new world as lacking human agency. Although they outwardly appear to be the same humans they were prior to infection with the new quasi-virus, they have, according to the survivors, lost their human agency. In traditional zombie films, grasping the loss of human agency is not particularly difficult. Zombies are humans stripped of the most central classical philosophical attributes that define humanity, namely self-consciousness and reason. They are beings enslaved to the most animalistic instincts of survival, devoid of language, rationality, and any capacity for moral judgment. In this sense, one may agree with Mary Campbell's claim that zombies are humans whose behaviors and motivations have been reduced to mechanically biological imperialism, and that we fear them precisely because they seek to turn us into themselves (Campbell, 1984, p. 310).

This line of thought leads directly to the radical definition of the human being articulated by Descartes at the dawn of modern philosophy. In traditional philosophy, rooted in Aristotelian doctrines, humans were distinguished from animals by virtue of possessing *logos* in their souls. Descartes, however, by positing a dualism between matter and mind, denied the existence of any soul in animals and regarded them as unconscious automata devoid of the capacity for thought and moral action, lacking language, and exhibiting behaviors that do not arise from thinking (Descartes, 1998, p. 32 AT VI 55–56)². Classical zombies can thus be understood as a feral version of Cartesian robots, operating according to the harshest laws of nature as a consequence of their lack of soul. The zombies of *Pluribus*, however, can hardly be classified within this simplified category of beings devoid of reason and self-consciousness. Contrary to what Descartes attributes to non-human material beings, they not only possess the capacity for linguistic communication, but—by virtue of their mastery of all human knowledge—are capable of speaking all the languages of the world. Moreover, contrary to the second criterion posited by Descartes, they not only possess the capacity for thought, but also exhibit distinctly rational behavior and demonstrate a firm commitment to moral principles.

Nor do the rational yet unconscious and emotionless beings introduced as philosophical zombies in the work of philosophers such as Chalmers (Kirk, 2023) bear much resemblance to the civilized zombies of *Pluribus*. The zombies of *Pluribus* are not only aware of what they say and do, but also display appropriate moral responses. They possess emotions, perceive tastes and smells, and act on an ethical concern to prevent environmental destruction. Even though they are aware that refraining from consuming animal flesh—or even plants—will result in insufficient nutrition and place their species at risk of extinction, they nonetheless refuse to engage in actions they consider immoral.

Yet the female protagonist of the series, Carol Sturka, as one of the survivors, persistently attempts to uncover something terrifying and criminal hidden behind the kind and civilized appearance of these beings. In one episode, she discovers a cold-storage facility in which, alongside fruits and other foodstuffs, dismembered human corpses are stored in packaged form. Horrified, yet exhilarated by what she believes to be the revelation of their criminal nature, she attempts to alert the other survivors.

This discovery, with its suspenseful tension, initially appears to be a narrative turning point that aligns the story with popular horror conventions. However, Carol—and the audience—soon realize that this suspense is deceptive. With commendable honesty, the civilized zombies explain that their refusal to kill living beings on Earth has led to severe food shortages, forcing them—against their own inclinations—to consume the bodies of animals and humans who have died through natural or accidental causes. Although Carol, like the audience, finds this practice repugnant, neither she nor the viewers can easily dismiss the logical—and perhaps even moral—force of their argument. Human corpses must either be buried or cremated, whereas they could instead be processed into an energizing liquid capable of providing the protein required by living humans, thereby preventing environmental destruction. Nevertheless, they assure Carol that they will never compel her to consume this horrifying food. They further promise to prepare, as far as possible, her favorite foods in order to keep her satisfied and content. These civilized zombies thus appear not only to be extraordinarily rational, logical, and knowledgeable, but also to act in an almost unbearably ethical manner.

Kantian Zombies: Rationality, Free Will, and Morality

The philosopher who can extricate us from the interpretive impasse posed by the zombies of *Pluribus* is Kant. Above all, Kant set aside Descartes' unsupported and problematic solution of dividing substances into material substance and thinking spirit, explicitly rejecting any form of spiritualist dualism and declaring belief in a thinking substance to be nothing more than a fallacy inherited from earlier philosophers (Kant, 1787/1998 A341/B399–A348/B406). Deeply influenced by the European Enlightenment, Kant sought to ground the mechanisms of knowledge, Consciousness, and self-consciousness on rational principles, without entangling himself in metaphysical concepts. Although he was a critic of German rationalist metaphysics—especially the Leibnizian–Wolffian tradition—he was equally determined not to become a mere continuation of non-rationalist European traditions such as British empiricism or French physicalism. His distinctive philosophical project, which he introduced under the name of transcendental philosophy, was an innovative form of rationalism based on the discovery of a priori principles of cognition—one that neither relied on metaphysical spiritualism nor fit within the framework of materialist rationalism. Kant's most decisive step in rationalism, however—the one that rendered him more radical than traditional rationalists—was his attempt to formulate morality and concepts such as Free will on the basis of a priori rational principles.

For Kant, morality was not merely a set of beliefs or empirical conventions governing collective human life; rather, its foundations were rooted in non-empirical and rational principles³. Kant understood morality as arising from a system of a priori principles produced by reason itself. Accordingly, he explicitly states that morality concerns not only human beings (as rational beings), but every being that possesses reason (Kant, 1788/2002 Ak 32). Human beings, therefore, are

bound by morality not because they are social beings who have adopted empirical principles for collective behavior, but because they are rational beings who, like all rational beings, are subject to the principles of reason. Like all other rational beings, humans possess not only reason but also will. For Kant, moral life is realized only when the will is determined by reason. The key concept here is freedom. From Kant's perspective, rational beings—including human beings—are precisely those beings for whom morality is applicable, insofar as they are simultaneously rational lawgivers and subject to the law (Kant, 1785/2008 Ak 4:431–432).

Rational beings, however, can institute the moral law only because they are free beings. Freedom is the pivotal concept in Kant's moral philosophy, yet Kant offers a distinctive and relatively unique account of freedom in comparison with earlier philosophers. In the philosophical tradition prior to Kant—a view that remains widespread even today—human freedom was defined in relation to the human will. On this account, humans are considered free insofar as they are able to choose between two actions or situations. For example, humans can choose whether to eat lunch or not, or whether to lie to a friend or tell the truth. Based on this conception of freedom, which goes back to Aristotle and later became foundational for theological eschatology in the Middle Ages, humans are rewarded or punished because they possess the capacity to choose between the right path and the wrong one. Kant's definition of freedom, by contrast, in both its negative and positive dimensions, rests entirely on the idea that freedom is a property of rational beings not because they can choose between alternatives, but because they are capable of liberating themselves from inclination and instinct and of making choices that run counter to the laws of nature.

For instance, a cat can also decide whether to climb a wall or take another path, or—despite hunger—decide to pursue a mate. For Kant, such capacities for choice have nothing to do with freedom. Climbing the wall or choosing another route, eating or pursuing a mate, are all different forms of biological self-interest imposed upon the cat by external natural laws. In reality, the cat's will is determined solely by something external to itself. Human beings, by contrast, are free not merely because they can choose between alternatives, but because they can choose something that offers them no natural advantage. Humans are free precisely because they can determine their will by reason rather than by inclination (Kant, 1785/2008 Ak 4:446–447). When humans determine their will not by inclinations that find satisfaction in nature, but by reason, they can act according to their own law rather than according to nature. In Kantian terms, they are capable of possessing autonomy rather than remaining bound by heteronomy.

Within this framework, moral action for Kant consists in freedom from the pathos of nature and in acting according to the laws of reason itself. From this perspective, any being capable of acting in accordance with laws derived from reason is a being capable of moral action. Yet when Kant insists that the moral law is not exclusive to human beings but applies equally to all rational beings, which other beings does he have in mind? In his own examples, following the tradition he inherited, Kant refers to God and angels. However, given that in the famous *Dialectic of Reason* section of the *Critique of Pure Reason* he regards all claims to knowledge of supernatural beings such as God and angels as mere speculative constructions of reason lacking any evidential support (Kant, 1787/1998 A636/B664), one may conclude that these examples serve merely as heuristic devices for the formulation of a philosophical system. In this system, Kant aims to construct a

conceptual function in its logical form. From this perspective, the different relations between will, inclination, and reason generate different states that philosophy must be prepared to articulate.

These states are not particularly numerous. In beings that lack reason, the will is always determined by inclination. This is precisely the condition depicted in traditional zombie films. Romero's zombies, having lost self-consciousness and reason, are entirely bound to their instinctual pathos and, like monsters operating solely on mechanical rules, constitute a threat. The second state is the human condition. Humans, because they can determine their will not only by inclination but also by reason, are confronted with moral challenges. If they determine their will by inclination (as, according to Kant, they do in most cases), they do not approach moral action; but if they can transcend the idea of freedom from natural pathos and from their inclination toward pleasure and avoidance of pain, they can become capable of understanding morality and of acting morally. In the third state, however, we may posit beings whose will is always determined by reason and never, under any circumstances, by inclination. These beings need not be devoid of inclination; it is sufficient that, despite having inclinations, they refrain from allowing inclination to determine their will. Had Kant lived long enough to watch *Pluribus*, he might have found better examples than God and angels. The zombies of *Pluribus* are precisely the beings Kant required.

The Holy Will

The zombies of *Pluribus* are human beings who, after a cosmic genetic intervention, have lost the capacity to lie, to be greedy, and to engage in all other forms of moral vice. In Kant's view, such vices arise because human beings determine their will not by reason, but by inclination. Inclination always seeks advantage and the immediate satisfaction of needs by whatever means lead most quickly to results, whereas reason acts solely on the basis of what is right and moral. Kant therefore concludes that if one can conceive of a rational being whose will is never determined by inclination but always by reason, then such a being would necessarily always act morally, on the basis of autonomy, without being subject to any external compulsion. Kant calls the will of such a being a "Holy Will" (Kant, 1788/2002 Ak 32). Accordingly, as Paton observes, a rational being with a holy will necessarily and spontaneously acts morally, without coercion (Paton, 1946, p. 116). It is precisely at this point that we are tempted to describe the rational and ethical zombies of *Pluribus* as Kantian zombies endowed with a holy will.

None of the Kantian zombies in *Pluribus* have lost self-consciousness as the result of an external intervention; in this respect, they are entirely different from the classical voodoo zombies. At the same time, they have by no means lost their self-consciousness or humanity, and in this regard they are fundamentally distinct from Romero's zombies. Unlike human beings, however—who, on the basis of their genetic and mental constitution, are capable of determining their will by inclination as well as by reason—they are capable only, and exclusively, of determining their will by the law of reason. Thus, whereas human beings at times violate moral laws such as "respect your neighbor," "promote the happiness of others," and "do not harm others" because their will is selfishly determined by inclination, the zombies of *Pluribus* always act in accordance with the rational moral law.

Kant was consistently concerned with the hope that human beings, by acting in accordance with the law of reason, might become more moral, and that human societies might thereby progress

toward what he calls the “Kingdom of ends” (Kant, 1785/2008 Ak 4:435). Yet he concluded that the realization of such a state could only be conceived as a regulative ideal—one that sustains human hope for a society of free, fully equal, and moral individuals—because in reality such a condition could occur only in an infinite temporal horizon (Kant, 1788/2002 Ak 122). In other words, it will never actually occur. Kant’s position is by no means grounded in philosophical pessimism; he is, on the contrary, a deeply optimistic philosopher who believes in the moral progress of humanity. Nevertheless, his analysis of human nature leads him to conclude that, since human beings can never fully free themselves from the pathos of inclination, they can never become entirely moral beings endowed with a holy will. *Pluribus*, however, appears to offer us the opportunity to witness a Kantian apocalypse without waiting for the gradual progress of history: an apocalypse grounded in a sudden transformation of human nature itself.

The event that produces the revolutionary transformation of human beings and human societies in *Pluribus*—an event that the transformed people themselves regard as the most important revolution in human history—has led to a new mode of ethical life that is in no way the result of external coercion. The transformed beings are not enchanted or bewitched creatures who have lost their self-consciousness or their memory, nor are they marionettes alienated from human life. They are aware of the changes that have occurred within them and are even capable of recalling their former human past; nevertheless, they prefer their new life, which, through a greater rupture with the laws of nature, is governed by ethical–rational principles. In this case, why should they be so strange that we are compelled to call them zombies at all? Why does the protagonist, Carol, constantly insist that they lack agency? And, finally, what harm does their rational and ethical mode of life inflict that drives Carol to such lengths in her attempt to restore the previous state of affairs?

Although the transformed humans in *Pluribus* possess self-consciousness, memory, and even emotions, they lack individuality and personal distinctness. This is precisely what terrifies Carol. They all possess the same knowledge, abilities, and skills (from cooking to piloting airplanes); they are simultaneously aware of the minds of all other humans; and instead of using “I,” they use “we.” Their minds constitute what may be described as a hive mind or a form of shared self-consciousness that contains all knowledge and is constantly aware of everything occurring in the world. In this respect, it closely resembles what philosophers such as al-Farabi and Avicenna—drawing on Greek commentators on Aristotle—called the Active intellect: a comprehensive and complete intellect to which human beings, at the highest level of intellectual perfection, could connect in order to apprehend truths (Fakhry, 2004, p. 165)⁴. Such a mind, however, carries the danger of eliminating personal differences and transforming human minds into a replicated colony of a single, unified, and perfect intellect.

The zombies of *Pluribus* exhibit no meaningful differences from one another. This becomes crucial for Carol when she falls in love with a beautiful woman among these zombies named Zosia. Carol directs special attention toward her, falls in love with her, and takes pleasure in their deep emotional bond. Zosia responds in the best possible way and falls in love with Carol as well. Yet when Carol realizes that Zosia loves all other humans in exactly the same way she loves Carol, she becomes disillusioned. What Carol seeks is love, and for her love acquires meaning within the logic of human difference. Zosia is different from others for Carol, but Carol is not different for Zosia. Zosia fulfills her moral duty to satisfy Carol in exactly the same way that she does for

everyone else. For Carol, Zosia thus lacks a deeply human dimension. From Carol's perspective, human morality is fully human only insofar as part of it is defined within the framework of the variable pathos of human inclination.

Certainly, Kant never intended to eliminate human differences to such an extent. Yet what occurs in *Pluribus* may be understood as the logical outcome of radicalizing and pushing Kant's moral philosophy to its extreme. Although Kant believed that human beings would never be fully liberated from the pathos of inclination, he nevertheless hoped that they might do so as far as possible through rational self-consciousness. In an extreme Kantian ethical model, therefore, love itself would have to become a moral matter, universally shared among all rational beings. What is sacrificed here is human individuality and personal distinctness. The human being Carol desires is not one who acts solely according to correct rational rules, but one who makes choices on the basis of the passion and excitement of inclination. It is for this reason that Carol can no longer endure the tedious world constructed by the Kantian zombies—a world devoid of desire-driven human beings whose very inclinations define their humanity and individuality.

Thus, what renders the society of Kantian zombies in *Pluribus* so profoundly inhuman is precisely that which has throughout the history of philosophy been regarded as the defining human characteristic: reason. Reason has been understood as that which distinguishes humans from animals; yet a universal and perfect reason, insofar as it sacrifices human individuality, ultimately empties human beings of their humanity. In this sense, Carol seeks to revive humanity by reintroducing certain non-rational dimensions of human life. She is, therefore, the figure who, in the post-apocalyptic Kantian world, finds the radical realization of Kantian reason entirely inhuman and attempts—by restoring the trajectory of reason's development—to save humanity itself.

Conclusion

The first season of *Pluribus* can readily be analyzed in a deep and systematic relation to the zombie film subgenre. In most zombie films, a strange event—such as biological intervention or genetic mutation—gives rise to beings who have been emptied of their humanity. Owing to its contagious nature, this event rapidly engulfs nearly the entire population, sparing only a small group of survivors and producing a post-apocalyptic world. These survivors attempt to preserve their humanity while seeking a way to overcome the crisis and restore the human condition. In its general structure, *Pluribus* fully conforms to this model. However, by inverting the genre's conventions, *Pluribus* arrives at a new definition of the zombie—one that stands in direct opposition to the zombie as a being devoid of rationality, language, and morality. In what *Pluribus* proposes, zombies are creatures of excessive rationality, whose ethical behavior itself is entirely framed by reason.

The definition of morality within the domain of reason constitutes one of the most important aspects of Kant's philosophy. In Kantian philosophy, morality is the result of the determination of the will by reason. Kant was fully aware that the human will can never be completely determined by reason alone, since human beings possess inclination in addition to reason. Nevertheless, Kant entertains the hypothesis that if a will were able to entirely avoid the pathos of inclination and be determined solely by reason, it could be described as a holy will—the ultimate telos of human life

in an eschatological horizon. *Pluribus* precisely stages this apocalypse: a world in which all human beings act on the basis of rational morality. Yet Carol, one of the survivors, experiences this condition as profoundly inhuman and seeks to restore humanity to the world. What Carol understands as humanity is the non-rational dimension of human life that preserves individuality and personal distinctness. Accordingly, Carol aims to transform the Kantian zombies into human beings endowed with desiring and non-rational dimensions. In this sense, although *Pluribus* follows the general framework of the zombie film, it becomes a philosophical challenge by overturning the very concepts that define what it means to be human and what it means to be a zombie.

¹ The original Latin phrase by Cicero is *ut unus fiat ex pluribus*, which Cicero formulated under the influence of Pythagoras.

² Descartes discusses this not only here but also in the *Meditations* and *Treatise on Man*. He considers animals as a type of Automata that are self-movers, and in this respect, they differ from machines assembled from parts, whose movement requires an external agent (Chene, 2015).

³ Kant often regarded empirical ethics as a Pragmatic Anthropology. Late in his life, his lecture series in this field was published under the title *Anthropology from a Pragmatic Point of View* (1798). As Manfred Kuehn points out, the young Kant, in the pre-critical period, still saw an intrinsic connection between pragmatic anthropology and ethics, but at least after 1775, and especially with the publication of the *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals* (1785), he reached the decisive conclusion that the foundations of ethics are entirely rational and should not be understood empirically. See also the introduction by Manfred Kuehn in (Kant, 1798/2006, p. xx).

⁴ The term *active intellect* (*intellectus activus*) was first introduced by Aristotle in *De Anima* to designate the immaterial and immortal aspect of human intellect. This concept was further developed by Alexander of Aphrodisias and later, in the Middle Ages, by philosophers such as Al-Farabi and Avicenna, who conceptualized it as an intellect distinct from human reason, to which the human mind must connect in order to apprehend philosophical truths. For further reading on this topic, see (Fakhry, 2004, pp. 125–166).

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